

An Overview of the Legal Framework for Incorporating Mediation into Civil Litigation in Tanzania

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Abstract:

This article analyzes the legal framework governing the use of mediation in Tanzania's civil litigation process. The article examines the role of domestic laws such as the Constitution of the United Republic of Tanzania, the Civil Procedure Code [Cap. 33 R.E. 2023], the Arbitration Act, the Employment and Labour Relations Act, and the Code of Conduct for Reconciliators, Negotiators, Mediators and Arbitrators, in entrenching mediation. The importance of mediation in the dispute settlement system and the role of the judiciary in promoting compliance with mediation procedures and fostering efficient, transparent dispute resolution are examined in this paper. The current framework for mediation is constrained by limited training of personnel involved mediation, weak awareness and enforcement, and minimal cooperation from advocates. The paper recommends enacting a comprehensive Mediation Act, strengthening mediator capacity, and institutionalizing monitoring mechanisms to enhance consistency and credibility. Ultimately, for mediation to achieve its intended purpose, Tanzania must combine legal reform with judicial commitment and a shift toward a participatory, integrity-based culture of dispute resolution.

Keywords: Mediation, Civil Litigation, Alternative Dispute Resolution, Tanzania.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Like in many common law jurisdictions, the civil litigation process in Tanzania is often characterized by prolonged procedures, case backlogs, and high litigation costs.¹ In response to these challenges, mediation was formally introduced into the Tanzanian legal system as an alternative dispute resolution (ADR) mechanism, primarily through amendments to the Civil Procedure Code². The intention was to enhance access to justice, reduce case backlog in courts, and promote amicable settlements between disputing parties.³ Despite the statutory recognition and procedural integration of mediation, particularly under Order VIII of the Civil Procedure Code⁴, its application and impact still have to be improved upon. This trend raises concerns about whether mediation is being used to its full potential to address the systemic inefficiencies in civil justice delivery.⁵ Reports and observations suggest that mediation is often treated as a mere formality, rather than a meaningful platform for dispute resolution.⁶ In some cases, parties fail to engage genuinely in the process, while in others, mediation is either rushed or inadequately facilitated, resulting in cases being returned to the litigation without settlement.⁷

2. HISTORICAL BACKGROUND OF USE OF MEDIATION IN CIVIL LITIGATION

Mediation was the first form of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) to be formally introduced in Tanzania in 1994 through Government Notice No. 422 of 1994, which amended the First Schedule to the Civil Procedure Code.⁸ Failure to pass through the mediation stage renders the whole proceedings a nullity, as was provided in the case of *Fahari Bottlers Limited and Another vs. Registrar of Companies and Another*,⁹ where it was held, “we are unable to understand why the rules relating to mediation were not observed in the case. I need to remind all concerned, that is, trial judges, magistrates, and advocates, that mediation not only facilitates the expeditious disposal of cases, but is less costly. Moreover, and this is important, mediation has no room for corrupt practices. Under mediation, the parties themselves decide their dispute under the guidance of the court. The transparent and participatory nature of the process makes it a very potent tool for the judiciary and the legal profession in combating corruption both at the Bar and the

¹ Lukumay, N. Z. (2016). A reflection on court-annexed mediation in Tanzania. *LST Law Review*, 1(1), 55–56.

² [Cap. 33 R.E. 2023]

³ Mpogole, J. (2020). The role of mediation in reducing case backlog in Tanzania. Tanzania Institute of Legal Practice.

⁴ Order VIIIIC Rule 24 of the Civil Procedure Code [Cap. 33 R.E 2023]

⁵ Didace, D. (2022). Alternative dispute resolution in Tanzania: Modes and challenges. Germany Library Publisher

⁶ Lukumay, supra note 1.

⁷ Mpogole, supra note 3

⁸ Cap. 33 [R.E. 2023] (originally enacted in 1966).

⁹ [2002] TLR 102.

Bench. This court expects to see better compliance with the relevant rules in the future.”¹⁰ Further legal recognition of mediation, as one of the major court-annexed Alternative Dispute Resolution processes,¹¹ was influenced by further amendments to the Civil Procedure Code in 2019.¹² Under the 2019 amendments, it is now mandatory¹³ for the court to refer every civil action to, *inter alia*, mediation,¹⁴ or an identical alternative procedure, before resorting to the proceedings of a trial.¹⁵ The increasing backlog of civil cases in Tanzanian courts has prompted judicial reforms aimed at promoting timely and efficient dispute resolution.¹⁶ One of the most significant reforms in this regard has been the institutionalization of mediation within the civil litigation process. Mediation, as a form of alternative dispute resolution (ADR), allows parties to a dispute to resolve their conflict amicably with the assistance of a neutral third party, thus reducing the burden on the formal court system. This paper sought to assess how effective mediation has been in achieving its intended goals within Tanzanian civil justice system.¹⁷

The subject matter of this paper revolves around court-annexed mediation and its legal framework, implementation practices, institutional capacity, and its perceived or measurable effectiveness in resolving civil disputes.

3. LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR MEDIATION

The legal framework governing court-annexed mediation in mainland Tanzania covers the national and international regimes on mediation that are relevant to Tanzania. These instruments are discussed in the next part of this paper.

3.1 The Constitution of the United Republic of Tanzania, 1977

The Constitution of the United Republic of Tanzania is the supreme law that establishes the judiciary’s authority to administer justice. Article 107A (1) vests final judicial authority in the judiciary, while Article 107A(2)(e) mandates courts to “promote and enhance dispute resolution among persons involved in the disputes.”¹⁸ This constitutional directive provides a strong foundation for incorporating mediation within Tanzania’s justice system. It promotes access to justice, efficiency, and amicable settlement as guiding judicial principles, thereby legitimizing mediation as a core value and encouraging judges to facilitate non-adversarial resolution. However, the Constitution does not provide detailed operational guidance for mediation, leaving its implementation dependent on subsidiary legislation, which has led to uneven application and weak

¹⁰Ibid

¹¹ The Civil Procedure Code, [Cap. 33 R.E. 2023]

¹²Civil Procedure Code (Amendment of the First Schedule) Rules, 2019 (Made under [Cap.33 R.E 2023])

¹³ Order VIII C Rule 24 of the Civil Procedure Code Act R.E. 2023.

¹⁴ *ibid*

¹⁵ *ibid*

¹⁶ Judiciary of Tanzania. (2020). Judiciary strategic plan 2020/2021–2024/2025. Judiciary of Tanzania.

¹⁷*ibid*.

¹⁸ Article 107A (1) and (2)(e). The Constitution of the United Republic of Tanzania, 1977.

enforcement of mediation outcomes. To strengthen constitutional intent and ensure consistency, it is recommended that Parliament enact a comprehensive Mediation Act explicitly anchored in Article 107A to institutionalize mediation as a constitutionally recognized process rather than a discretionary option.¹⁹

3.2 The Civil Procedure Code [CAP 33 R.E 2023]

In Tanzania, mediation is primarily regulated under the Civil Procedure Code,²⁰ with the exception of land and labor cases, which are governed by separate regulatory frameworks at lower judicial levels. Notably, Rule 3 of Order VIIIA of the Civil Procedure Code²¹ authorizes the use of the Alternative Dispute Resolution process as part of the civil litigation system. It provides that once pleadings are concluded, efforts should be made to resolve the dispute through mediation, arbitration, negotiation, or other alternative mechanisms before proceeding to trial. But in reality, courts only actively use mediation under the Civil Procedure Code, which was amended.²²

The Civil Procedure Code,²³ also sets out the procedural framework for handling civil cases, including provisions on court-annexed mediation. Section 64 of the Act²⁴ provides that, unless otherwise specified by the Arbitration Act or any other written law, all references to arbitration shall be governed by the Second Schedule. More importantly, Order VIIC, Rule 24 directs that every civil action be referred to negotiation, conciliation, mediation, arbitration, or a similar alternative procedure before trial, subject to the provisions of written law.²⁵ The Second Schedule further outlines procedures relating to arbitration, while court-annexed mediation applies broadly to civil claims, except in limited matters such as election petitions, constitutional, human rights cases and family maintenance disputes.²⁶

Although this framework strongly embeds mediation within the civil litigation process and reflects the legislature's intention to promote faster and less adversarial dispute resolution, its effectiveness in practice remains limited. Court-annexed mediation has not consistently achieved its goals in Tanzania, largely due to implementation challenges such as insufficient trained mediators, lack of awareness among litigants, and uneven application across courts.²⁷ As a result, mediation is often treated as a procedural

¹⁹ Mashamba, C. J., *Alternative Dispute Resolution: Law and Practice* (Mkuki na Nyota Publishers, 2020), p. 51.

²⁰ Orders VIIIA, VIIIB, and VIIC of The Civil Procedure Code [Cap.33 R.E 2023]

²¹ Cap.33 [R.E 2023]

²² Government Notice No. 5A of 2023.

²³ *Supra*, note 166

²⁴ Order VIIC Rule 24 *Supra* note 39

²⁵ Section 64, of the Civil Procedure Code [Cap.33 R.E 2023]

²⁶ Hazel, G. (2010), (June). Civil Mediation: A measured approach? *Journal of Judicial Studies Institute*, 10(1), 1-26.

²⁷ Mtukusye, A. I. (2024). Challenges facing the implementation of court-annexed mediation in the Commercial Division of the High Court of Tanzania. *International Journal of Law, Management & Humanities*, 7(5), 117-141

formality rather than a genuinely effective mechanism for resolving civil disputes, and the potential benefits envisioned under the Act have yet to be fully realized.²⁸ Three ADR techniques: negotiation, mediation, and arbitration are listed under Order VIIIA Rule 3 (1).²⁹ The same rule does, however, allow for the adoption of alternative techniques that are not expressly covered by the phrase, such as other procedures that do not include a trial. Nonetheless, there is opportunity to employ more techniques not yet described.

3.3 The Arbitration Act [Cap. 15 R.E. 2023]

Although primarily focused on arbitration, the Arbitration Act indirectly supports mediation by promoting out-of-court settlements and the enforcement of arbitral awards. Section 4 of the Act permits disputes to be referred to arbitration or other forms of alternative dispute resolution in accordance with the parties' agreement, thereby reinforcing party autonomy and the freedom to choose mediation as a private and consensual mechanism for dispute resolution.³⁰ However, the Act's limited reference to mediation creates conceptual ambiguity between mediation and arbitration, as it fails to adequately distinguish the non-binding, facilitative nature of mediation from the determinative and binding nature of arbitration. To address this gap, future legal reform should introduce a dedicated Mediation and Conciliation Chapter within the Act or, preferably, a standalone Mediation Act that clearly defines mediation procedures, outlines the enforceability of settlement agreements, and establishes qualifications and ethical standards for mediators.³¹

3.4 The Employment and Labour Relations Act (ELRA) R.E 2023.

The Employment and Labour Relations Act institutionalizes mediation as a key mechanism for resolving labour disputes through Section 86, which requires that all such disputes be referred to the Commission for Mediation and Arbitration (CMA) before proceeding to arbitration or litigation.³² This provision establishes mediation as a mandatory first step in labour dispute resolution, ensuring a swift, cost-effective, and accessible process facilitated by specialized officers operating within structured timelines. Despite these strengths, the effectiveness of mediation under the ELRA is sometimes undermined by overburdened and inadequately trained mediators, which can lead to rushed settlements and ineffective facilitation. In *Amina Haji v Tanzania Ports Authority*³³. The Commission for Mediation and Arbitration (CMA) emphasized that mediation is a compulsory precondition to arbitration and promotes industrial harmony

²⁸ Lukumay, Z. N. (2016). A reflection on court-annexed mediation in Tanzania. *The Law School of Tanzania Journal*, 1(2), 51-60

²⁹The Civil Procedure Code [Cap 33 R.E 2023].

³⁰ Section 4 of Arbitration Act, Cap. 15 [R.E. 2023]

³¹ Menkel-Meadow, C., (2011) "Why and When to Use Mediation or Other Forms of Dispute Resolution in the Legal Process," *Georgetown Law Journal* p. 10.

³² Section 86(1) of the Employment and Labour Relations Act, No. 6 of 2004 R.E 2023.

³³ (Labour Dispute CMA/DSM/ILA/352/2018).

through voluntary settlement. In addition, some mediations fail due to limited cooperation from parties or insufficient understanding of the process.³⁴ To enhance the credibility and quality of CMA proceedings, it is essential to provide regular professional training for mediators, ensure adequate staffing, and enforce strict adherence to mediation ethics and procedural standards.³⁵

3.5 The Labour Institutions Act, R.E 2023

The Labour Institutions Act complements the Employment and Labour Relations Act by establishing the institutional framework for labour dispute resolution, including the provision of mediation services. Section 14 of the Act mandates the Registrar of Labour Institutions to maintain a list of qualified mediators and arbitrators, thereby ensuring that only competent individuals handle such matters.³⁶ Through this structure, the Act institutionalizes mediation within recognized bodies, promoting administrative oversight, consistency, and professionalism in dispute resolution. However, its effectiveness is often weakened by limited funding, inadequate monitoring mechanisms, and insufficient evaluation of mediators' performance, which collectively undermine accountability and the overall quality of mediation outcomes. In *Kabanga Nickel Co. Ltd v Commissioner for Labour*,³⁷ the court reaffirmed that mediation outcomes must respect party autonomy and cannot be imposed unilaterally by mediators. To address these shortcomings, the learned author, Mashamba has said that regulatory supervision should be strengthened through periodic performance reviews, enhanced capacity building, and the introduction of public reporting mechanisms on mediation outcomes to improve transparency, accountability, and public trust in the process.³⁸

3.6 The Code of Conduct for Reconciliators, Negotiators, Mediators and Arbitrators, 2021

The Code of Conduct for Reconciliators, Negotiators, Mediators and Arbitrators establishes ethical and professional standards that guide mediators in performing their duties with confidentiality, impartiality, and competence.³⁹ By emphasizing neutrality, voluntary participation, and respect for party autonomy, the Code promotes professionalism and enhances confidence in the mediation process. Nonetheless, the effectiveness of the Code is hindered by weak enforcement mechanisms, as breaches of

³⁴ Mtukusye, A. I., (2024), "Challenges Facing the Implementation of Court-Annexed Mediation in the Commercial Division of the High Court of Tanzania," *International Journal of Law, Management & Humanities*, p. 217.

³⁵ Didace, D., (2022). *Alternative Dispute Resolution in Tanzania: Modes and Challenges* (Germany Library Publisher, p. 96.

³⁶ Section 14, Labour Institutions Act, Cap. 300 [R.E. 2023].

³⁷ HC Labour Division, 2021.

³⁸ Mashamba, C. J., (2020) *Alternative Dispute Resolution: Law and Practice* (Mkuki na Nyota Publishers. p. 94.

³⁹ Rule 4-8 of the Code of Conduct for Reconciliators, Negotiators, Mediators and Arbitrators, 2021.

its provisions often go unreported or unsanctioned.⁴⁰ To ensure adherence to these ethical standards, it is recommended that a National Mediation Accreditation Board be established under the Ministry of Justice or the Judiciary to oversee compliance, accredit mediators, enforce disciplinary measures where necessary, and uphold the integrity and credibility of the mediation profession in Tanzania.⁴¹

3.7 UNCITRAL Model on Conciliation and Mediation

According to Article 5, mediation proceedings concerning a disagreement should begin on the day the parties agree to participate.⁴² The invitation to mediate may be deemed rejected by the party that sent the invitation if they do not hear back from the other party within 30 days of the invitation being sent or within any other time frame mentioned in the invitation. The disputant chooses how the mediation process is conducted; if they cannot agree, the mediator proceeds in whatever way he sees fit. Information about the mediation process is confidential and cannot be used in court.⁴³

3.8 East African Community Mediation Agreement, 1984

The East African Community has adopted instruments that encourage and shape mediation as a dispute-resolution tool among member states. The East African Community Mediation Agreement provide a regional legal basis for mediation initiatives and signals member states' commitment to ADR as part of regional cooperation and dispute-management strategies⁴⁴. This regional posture helps harmonize expectations about mediation, encourages cross-border ADR practice, and creates a normative environment that national courts (including Tanzania's) can draw on.⁴⁵

3.9 The East African Court of Justice Rules of Procedure, 2019

The East African Court of Justice Rules of Procedure explicitly incorporates ADR in its procedural rules: The Court may direct parties to mediation or other settlement processes during case management and scheduling conferences. The EACJ's use of ADR demonstrates how a regional court operationalizes mediation, sets procedural models (e.g., timing, referral practice), and builds institutional capacity that national judiciaries can emulate.⁴⁶

⁴⁰ Hamis, T. H.,(2022) "Court-Annexed Mediation in Tanzania: Success, Challenges and Prospects," International Journal of Innovative Research and Advanced Studies. p. 112.

⁴¹ Lukumay, Z. N., (2022). Utatuzi wa Migogoro kwa Njia ya Maridhiano (ExcellentOne Graphics & Print), p. 88.

⁴²Article 5 of the UNCITRAL Model on Conciliation and Mediation.

⁴³Ibid,

⁴⁴ Article 1-4 of The East African Community Mediation Agreement, 1984

⁴⁵Article 5(1) and 28 of the Treaty for the Establishment of the East African Community (1999)

⁴⁶ Rule 64 of the East African Court of Justice Rules of Procedure, 2019

4. CHALLENGES TO THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MEDIATION IN THE CIVIL LITIGATION PROCESS

4.1 Judicial capacity and conflict of roles

The Civil Procedure Code,⁴⁷ entrusts mediation to judicial officers, many of whom lack specialized training in facilitative mediation techniques. In practice, some judges or magistrates adopt quasi-adjudicatory approaches rather than neutral facilitation.⁴⁸ This judicial dominance creates role conflict: a judicial officer who fails to settle a case as mediator may later preside over the same case as adjudicator, raising questions of neutrality and party trust.⁴⁹ When judges or registrars act as mediators, the process often fails due to their limited experience and training in mediation. The specialized skills required for effective mediation differ significantly from the traditional adjudicative methods with which judicial officers are more familiar, thereby affecting the overall success of the mediation process.⁵⁰

Judges are usually taught to settle cases using the traditional “winner takes all, loser loses all” strategy. This way of thinking, however, is incompatible with the idea of amicable settlements, which advocate for compromise between the parties and a “winner wins a little, loser loses a little” conclusion.⁵¹ Since many judges and court registrars have a litigation-focused mindset and can be unduly strict, this dual function makes it difficult to reach agreeable outcomes. Because many judges find it difficult to put aside their antagonistic attitudes during mediation, the dual roles of mediator and judge can result in inadequate dispute resolution. Furthermore, parties may feel uneasy during mediation sessions and participate less actively in the process as a result of judges perceived authority and respect.⁵²

4.2 Lack of enough cooperation from advocates

The findings found that because advocates frequently fail to help their clients to reach a mutually agreeable conclusion, they contribute to the inefficiency of court-annexed mediation. Due to the possibility of receiving significant litigation fees, they are more likely to move forward with a full trial. Usually, these fees are determined by managing various applications, handling the suit, filing and handling it, making appearances, drafting, and giving legal advice. Since the matter would not go to trial, many advocates

⁴⁷ [Cap. 33 R.E 2023]

⁴⁸ Hamis, T. H. (2022). Court-annexed mediation in Tanzania: Success, challenges and prospects. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Advanced Studies*, 9(11), 41-47.

⁴⁹ Njeru, E. M. (2017). Judicial role conflicts in mediation: An African perspective. *Journal of African Law*, 61(3), 389-408.

⁵⁰ Lukumay, Z. N. (2016). A reflection on court-annexed mediation in Tanzania. *LST Law Review*, 1(1), 92-94.

⁵¹ p. 55, *ibid*

⁵² Hamis, T. (2022) Court-Annexed Mediation in Tanzania: Successes, Challenges and Prospects. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Advanced Studies (IJIRAS)* Volume 9 Issue 11, November, 2022, p.12

fear that helping their clients reach a settlement through mediation could result in a financial loss.⁵³ The way these litigation lawyers bill their clients, some on an hourly basis, while others charge for each day they appear in court, often influence this way of thinking.⁵⁴ Advocates, who serve as the parties' lead advisors, usually do not work with judges or registrars to ensure the mediation process is successful because they frequently discourage the adoption of amicable conflict settlement for their own purposes. Advocates' lack of collaboration reduces mediation's efficacy and jeopardizes its chances of success.⁵⁵

5. CONCLUSION

While Tanzania has made commendable progress in institutionalizing mediation within its civil justice system, the process remains largely procedural rather than transformative. Sustainable effectiveness will depend on the political will of policymakers, the commitment of the judiciary, and the active participation of advocates and ADR institutions in fostering a mediation culture grounded in professionalism, neutrality, and mutual respect. When supported by a coherent legislative and institutional framework, mediation can evolve into a cornerstone of Tanzania's quest for an accessible, efficient, and people-centered justice system.

There is need for the government, in collaboration with the judiciary, to develop and enact a Mediation Act. Such legislation would provide detailed guidance on core issues including confidentiality, enforcement of settlement agreements, ethical obligations of mediators, timelines, and record-keeping. A standalone Act would strengthen the legal framework, enhance predictability, and institutionalize mediation as a substantive dispute resolution mechanism rather than a procedural formality.

In addition, judicial officers and other appointed mediators should undergo systematic training in facilitative mediation techniques. Training should emphasize impartiality, communication skills, conflict management, and party-centered approaches. Furthermore, continuous professional development programs should be institutionalized to ensure mediators remain equipped with modern skills and approaches. Consideration should also be given to appointing dedicated, professionally trained mediators instead of relying exclusively on judicial officers.

⁵³ Menkel-Meadow, C. (2011). Why and when to use mediation or other forms of dispute resolution in the legal process. *Georgetown Law Journal*, 100(3), 881–924

⁵⁴Brooker, P and Lavers, A (2000). Appropriate ADR: Identifying Features of Construction Dispute Which Affect Their Suitability for Submission to ADR', *International Construction Law Review*, vol. 12, no. 2, p. 272-295

⁵⁵McEwen, CA, Rogers, NH and Maiman, RJ (1995), 'Bring in the Lawyers: Challenging the Dominant Approaches to Ensuring Fairness in Divorce Mediation', *Minnesota Law Review*, vol. 79, p. 1317-1411

It is also important for the judiciary to emphasize the voluntary nature of mediation through public sensitization campaigns, orientation sessions for litigants, and clear communication of rights and processes. Parties should perceive mediation not as a compulsory procedural hurdle but as a genuine opportunity to resolve disputes amicably. This shift requires both judicial attitude change and greater awareness among litigants and legal practitioners. Furthermore, partnerships or collaboration between the judiciary, law schools, bar associations, and ADR institutions should be strengthened to promote best practices, research, and knowledge exchange. Such collaboration would also help to build a broader culture of mediation beyond court processes.